

Example Sounds

The example sounds are built with the geometry on a membrane with 10 cm diameter and the respective material parameters, except for the tension which was reduced to half the tension in the paper to make the sound deeper. The five example sounds below change viscoelasticity at certain frequency bands to vary the sound, and to show the relation to a metal plate with high-frequency damping tuned down. This last case is no longer realistic for a drum, but shows the transition between instruments is often caused by internal damping.

Sound 1: Reference sound, a drum with fundamental frequency 210 Hz.

Viscoelastically damped frequencies:

- 1) 250 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$
- 2) 700 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$
- 3) 1000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 4) 1500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 5) 2000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 6) 2500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 7) 3000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.02$
- 8) 3300 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 9) 4100 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 10) 5000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 11) 6400 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 12) 6750 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 13) 7500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$
- 14) 12000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.5$
- 15) 16000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.33$

Sound 2: With increased energy in the 3.3 kHz and 4.1 kHz Band. This sound is like a which has an additional metal stick beaten, too, like a rim shot of a snare drum.

Viscoelastically damped frequencies:

- 1) 250 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$
- 2) 700 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$
- 3) 1000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 4) 1500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 5) 2000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 6) 2500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 7) 3000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.02$
- 8) 3300 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 9) 4100 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 10) 5000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 11) 6400 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 12) 6750 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 13) 7500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$
- 14) 12000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.5$
- 15) 16000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.33$

Sound 3: A sound with hand damping the drum, where the lowest frequency is gone fast, while a higher frequency around 500 Hz still remains

Viscoelastically damped frequencies:

- 1) 250 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0003$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$**
- 2) 700 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$

- 3) 1000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 4) 1500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 5) 2000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 6) 2500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 7) 3000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.02$
- 8) 3300 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 9) 4100 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 10) 5000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 11) 6400 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 12) 6750 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 13) 7500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$
- 14) 12000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.5$
- 15) 16000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.33$

Sound 4: Here the third partial of the drum around 770 Hz is enhanced, varying the reference sound only slightly

Viscoelastically damped frequencies:

- 1) 250 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$
- 2) 700 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00002$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.001$**
- 3) 1000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 4) 1500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 5) 2000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 6) 2500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 7) 3000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.02$
- 8) 3300 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 9) 4100 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 10) 5000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 11) 6400 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 12) 6750 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$
- 13) 7500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$
- 14) 12000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.5$
- 15) 16000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.33$

Sound 5: With high frequencies damped less, and lower frequencies damped more, the sound is similar to a metal plate

Viscoelastically damped frequencies:

- 1) 250 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.0001$**
- 2) 700 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 3) **1000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 4) **1500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 5) **2000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 6) **2500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00002$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.02$**
- 7) **3000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$**
- 8) **3300 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 9) **4100 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 10) **5000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 11) **6400 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 12) **6750 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.00005$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.01$**
- 13) **7500 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0001$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.1$**
- 14) **12000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.5$**
- 15) **16000 Hz, $\text{Re}\{E(s)\} = 0.0008$, Laplace $\gamma = 0.33$**